

Preliminary Assessment of Israel's Intelligence Failure: Strategic Surprise and Deception on 7 October 2023

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ABSTRACT

A case-study of Israel's intelligence failure of 7 October 2023 identifies strategic surprise and deception, the breakdown of the devil's advocate system, and Israeli hubris in policy as foundational flaws in intelligence tradecraft. The events of 7 October 2023, ostensibly avoidable through more robust intelligence foresight, nevertheless resulted in a successful and violent tactical assault with regional repercussions. A key takeaway from this case is that the fostering of continuous critical review and scenario testing within the intelligence community (IC) addresses blind spots and anticipates unconventional and otherwise unimaginable threats to national security.

KEYWORDS: Surprise, Deception, Denial, Intelligence, Failures, Terrorism, Hamas, Israel

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On 7 October 2023, Hamas attacked Israel, causing an Israeli response that would shatter regional diplomatic relations and the global stance on Middle Eastern politics. Israel's profound misjudgment of Hamas's intentions and capabilities laid the groundwork for a tactical assault that sparked a high-intensity regional war. Hamas's 7 October

2023 attack serves as a poignant case study of the complexities of strategic surprise—specifically, the foundational stratagem of denial and deception used to accomplish it. This paper examines the multifaceted situation that led to Hamas's shockingly successful execution of aggression, elucidating intelligence failures, policy shortcomings, and the

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fallacies that contributed to this catalyst of retaliatory war against Hamas.¹ Ultimately, Hamas employed denial and deception to achieve 7 October 2023. However, by analyzing the intricate dynamics of the lead-up to the attack, this paper provides insight into the Israeli policy failure and hubris that, together with denial and deception, led to 7 October 2023’s catastrophic success.

Surprise and Deception

While the goals of surprise and deception range from wartime campaigning to influencing peacetime action, it is clear that Hamas’s use of these maneuvers instigated an existentially-charged response. Strategic surprise is an unexpected policy, manifested in technological innovation, unexpected military moves, and/or tactical engagements, leveraged to catch an adversary off-guard.² Deception, rapid changes in technology and operations, and intelligence failures occur in a broader strategic context, resulting in surprise and a fundamental altering of the international status quo.

Deception is the deliberate misleading of information and intentions through distortion, informational manipulation, denial, and concealment.³ This strategy relies upon the intentional misdirection of targets, the use of military feints and decoys, the hiding of true

capabilities and movements, and double agents. These false and misleading actions, intentions, and intelligence are skillfully employed to achieve the deception.⁴ For the weaker party in a conflict, deception is an essential tactic, as it manipulates perceptions of reality.⁵ Denial, meanwhile, is a component of deception in which information channels are obstructed so that adversaries cannot gain insight into counter operations. As defined by Abram Shulsky, denial “refers to the attempt to block all information channels by which an adversary could learn some truth... thus preventing him from reacting in a timely manner.”⁶ In examining the role of denial and deception within the overall intelligence failures of 10/7, Hamas leveraged denial and deception to achieve strategic surprise over Israel.

Background / Status Quo

Hamas is a Palestinian Islamist militant group which has effectively ruled over the Gaza Strip since January 2006. The group was founded during the 1987 Intifada, emerging as a powerful offshoot of the Muslim Brotherhood.⁷ Hamas advocates for an Islamic State in Gaza and the West Bank; while it governs Gaza, Fatah rules over the West Bank. Hamas began as a resistance and activist group, but it now functions as a political, ideological, and military power.⁸ Its

¹ Hu, Hadas Gold, Shirin Faqiri, Helen Regan, Jessie Yeung, Caitlin. 2023. “Israel Formally Declares War against Hamas as It Battles to Push Militants off Its Soil.” CNN. October 8, 2023.

² Shultz, Richard. “Strategic Surprise and Deception.” 21st Century Intelligence Seminar. Class lecture at the Fletcher at Tufts University, Medford, MA, 1 April 2023.

³ Shultz, “Strategic Surprise and Deception.”

⁴ Chadwick, Andrew, and James Stanyer. 2021. “Deception as a Bridging Concept in the Study of Disinformation, Misinformation, and Misperceptions: Toward a Holistic Framework.” *Communication Theory* 32 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/ct/qtab019>: 2.

⁵ Shulsky, Abram. Elements of Strategic Denial and Deception. Trends in Organized Crime, Volume 6, 2000: 15.

⁶ Shulsky, Elements of Strategic Denial and Deception. Trends in Organized Crime: 15.

⁷ Kali Robinson, “What Is Hamas?” *Council on Foreign Relations*, 17 Oct. 2024, available at www.cfr.org/backgrounder/what-hamas, accessed 19 Mar. 2025.

⁸ National Counterterrorism Center, “National Counterterrorism Center | FTOs,” *Office of the Director of National Intelligence*, Sept. 2022, available at www.dni.gov/nctc/ftos/hamas_fto.html, accessed 19 Mar. 2025.

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military wing, Izz ad-Din al-Qassam Brigades, rules over Gazan schools, charities, aid, and hospitals. Hamas does not recognize Israel and opposes its right to exist, calling for its destruction.⁹ The group has carried out shootings and suicide terrorist attacks against Israel, which instigated Israeli blockades on Gaza.

In 2005, Israel unilaterally withdrew from the Gaza Strip; Hamas assumed power in the remaining void. After Israel left Gaza, tensions with Hamas remained high. In 2014, after the death of three Israelis in the West Bank by Hamas-affiliates,¹⁰ Israel launched Operation Protective Edge (also known as the Gaza War).¹¹ This two-month-long conflict was one of the deadliest contemporary conflicts between Israel and Hamas until 7 October 2023, with 2,000 lives lost.¹² The 2014 war ended with a general ceasefire,¹³ and Israel acted to effectively manage conflict with no active hostilities other than rocket launchings in the following nine years. This baseline activity set the stage for strategic surprise, as Israel shifted its focus to the West Bank.

7 October 2023

Early in the morning of 7 October 2023, Hamas paragliders flew over the border into Israel while gunmen “stormed Israeli bases and communities.”¹⁴ They “exploded drones to disable Israel’s border security architecture,”¹⁵ effectively blinding the IDF groups monitoring border sensors. Israeli control center communications were rendered powerless and completely cut off, while the IDF Gaza Division Headquarters were invaded. Hamas launched 2,000 rockets as an operational cover, while the gunmen began a violent land invasion. These militants followed maps made by Gazans working in Israel or obtained through Google Maps to guide their assault.¹⁶ They attacked kibbutzim—small Israeli towns—near the border with Gaza, as well as the Re’im Supernova Sukkot Music Festival, killing over 1,200 Israelis and taking another 240 hostage.¹⁷ This was the largest instance of specifically Jewish deaths since the Holocaust, and the most deadly terror attack against the State of Israel since its founding in the mid-20th century.¹⁸

⁹ “Doctrine of Hamas,” Wilson Center, 20 Oct. 2023, available at www.wilsoncenter.org/article/doctrine-hamas, accessed 19 Mar. 2025.

¹⁰ Shelby Lin Erdman, “Israeli Authorities Identify the Suspects in Teens’ Kidnapping,” *CNN*, 26 June 2014, available at www.cnn.com/2014/06/26/world/meast/israel-kidnapped-teenagers-hamas/index.html, accessed 19 Mar. 2025.

¹¹ Raphael S. Cohen, David E. Johnson, David E. Thaler, Brenna Allen, Elizabeth M. Bartels, James Cahill, and Shira Efron, “Lessons from Israel’s Wars in Gaza,” *RAND Corporation*, 18 Oct. 2017, available at www.rand.org/pubs/research_briefs/RB9975.html, accessed 19 Mar. 2025.

¹² Mairav Zonszein, “Israel Killed More Palestinians in 2014 than in Any Other Year since 1967,” *The Guardian*, 27 Mar. 2015, available at www.theguardian.com/world/2015/mar/27/israel-kills-more-palestinians-2014-than-any-other-year-since-1967, accessed 19 Mar. 2025.

¹³ Sherwood, Harriet, and Hazem Balousha. “Gaza Ceasefire: Israel and Palestinians Agree to Halt Weeks of Fighting.” *The Guardian*. August 27, 2014.

¹⁴ Hubbard, Ben, and Maria Abi-Habib. 2023. “Behind Hamas’s Bloody Gambit to Create a ‘Permanent’ State of War.” *The New York Times*, November 8, 2023, sec. World.

¹⁵ Hubbard, “Behind Hamas’s Bloody Gambit to Create a ‘Permanent’ State of War.”

¹⁶ Flamer, Netanel. “Counterintelligence: the Case of Hamas on 7 October 2023.” *21st Century Intelligence Seminar*. Class lecture at the Fletcher at Tufts University, Medford, MA, 8 April 2023.

¹⁷ Vinograd, Cassandra, and Isabel Kershner. 2023. “Israel’s Attackers Took about 240 Hostages. Here’s What to Know About Them.” *The New York Times*, November 4, 2023, sec. World.

¹⁸ Byman, Daniel, Riley McCabe, Alexander Palmer, Catrina Doxsee, Mackenzie Holtz, and Delaney Duff. “Hamas’s

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Since 7 October 2023, Hamas was able to catalyze an Israeli existential crisis and disrupt the status quo of regional conflict. Its actions and achievement of strategic surprise confounded Israel's perceptions of the foreseeable future between it and Hamas. The retaliation in Gaza furthers the success of Hamas's surprise, as implications of Israeli engagement include social upheaval and a global divide over the seemingly 'mutually exclusive' rights of Palestinians and Israelis. The strategic advantage of war and surprise placed Hamas in a position of power over Israel, which was, and remains, emotionally overwhelmed.

Yom Kippur War

Hamas's surprise was not a unique instance of successful surprise in Israel. A prior instance of strategic surprise in Israel includes the Yom Kippur War of October, 1973, which historically mirrors some strategies employed by Hamas on 7 October 2023. Hamas may have tried to emulate the successful strategies used by the Egyptians and Syrians in 1973, which worked successfully on a scale beyond perhaps envisioned by the attack planners. On a Jewish High Holiday (Yom Kippur), Egypt and Syria launched a surprise attack to regain territories previously lost in the Golan Heights and the Sinai Peninsula.¹⁹ The Arab coalition's success was due in large part to the deception they used to catch Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) off-guard.²⁰ Much of the IDF was observing the holiday, so its manpower was

minimal. Additionally, Israel was convinced that an attack was unlikely due to recent Egyptian military exercises, and no observable signs of Syrian war preparations.²¹ This Israeli 'concept' concluded that Arab armies would not attack until all participants' capabilities could counter Israeli air superiority, so Syria would not attack until Egypt felt capable. The Yom Kippur War had significant geopolitical implications; despite its end in stalemate, this conflict opened the diplomatic arena for the Camp David Accords,²² and also underscored the importance of the Israeli military's preparation for surprise. Importantly, in relation to 7 October 2023, a contemporary consequence of the Yom Kippur War was that Hamas heeded the lessons of history, while Israel did not.

Comparison

Like last century's surprise attack, Hamas's 7 October 2023 offensive occurred during the High Holiday Season: 7 October 2023 ended the month of the highest of Jewish holy days, Rosh Hashanah, Yom Kippur, and Sukkot. More specifically, the morning of 7 October 2023 marked the end of Sukkot and the beginning of the celebratory Shemini Atzeret and Simchat Torah. In Israel, major Jewish holidays are adopted as national holidays. Like the Yom Kippur War, many IDF reservists were on holiday break. Shemini Atzeret is commemorated by not working, and Simchat Torah is a celebration of the Torah through festive dancing and singing.²³

October 7 Attack: Visualizing the Data." CSIS. 19 December 2023.

¹⁹ Rabinovich, Itamar. "Israel's 1973 October War: A 50-Year Perspective." Brookings. October 3, 2023.

²⁰ Rabinovich, "Israel's 1973 October War: A 50-Year Perspective."

²¹ Riedel, Bruce. "Enigma: The Anatomy of Israel's Intelligence Failure Almost 45 Years Ago." Brookings. September 25, 2017.

²² Rabinovich, "Israel's 1973 October War: A 50-Year Perspective."

²³ "Simchat Torah: A Jewish Holiday of Reading, Renewal and Resilience." Colorado Arts and Sciences Magazine. October 14, 2022.

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Additionally, 7 October 2023 was not only a weekend day, but a Saturday—the Sabbath. For observant Jews, no work is done on Shabbat and people refrain from using modern technology. Together, these factors minimized the IDF's readiness and put those working at a disadvantage, as there was less manpower available to immediately mobilize.

Similar to the Yom Kippur War, Israel did not believe that imminent attacks by Hamas were credible: while its intelligence gatherings alerted of the possibility of conflict, Israeli officials dismissed these warnings as beyond Hamas's capabilities and not aligned with assumed intent. The role of advanced notification and its dismissal, in both 7 October 2023 and the Yom Kippur War was instrumental in the adversary's successful strategic surprise. The goal of many intelligence operations lies within the ability to forewarn of military, political, social, and economic issues.²⁴ However, surprise and deception inhibit the role of warning in intelligence. In the case of 7 October 2023, Israel assumed that Hamas could not attack to such a scale, but ignored irrationality of intent: the rationality of Hamas's leadership and attack planners is unknown. Further, the leadership's strategic logic for the attack and its goals are not clear. Likewise, during the Yom Kippur War, intelligence assessments were dismissed due to presumed limited capabilities. During the Yom

Kippur War, analysts aroused concern of Egyptian military exercises, but Israeli senior intelligence and military officials believed Egypt would not attack until it could directly challenge Israeli air superiority.²⁵ The IDF also believed that Syria would not attack until Egypt did. These assessments were futile, as Egypt worked around its capabilities and joined with Syria to attack in ways unimagined by the IDF: land-based mobile anti-air systems challenged the Israeli Air Force.²⁶ Similarly, 7 October 2023 resulted in the failure of conflating the assessment of capabilities with the assessment of intention.

Devil's Advocate

Moreover, with the conclusion of Yom Kippur War hostilities, the Israeli military intelligence created the Devil's Advocate Unit.²⁷ The goal of the Devil's Advocate Unit was to institutionalize contrarian questioning of intelligence assessments. Early warnings of assault by Hamas were issued by Israeli and foreign intelligence, but these alarms were brushed aside.²⁸ Unlike the complete ambush of the Yom Kippur War, the IDF had received alert and documentation of Hamas's attack plan, which they nicknamed 'Jericho Wall,' a year in advance of 7 October 2023.²⁹ The 40-page, detailed plan was a "point by point"³⁰ outline of the destruction that would ensue on 7 October 2023. The document was circulated among the Israeli

²⁴ Shultz, "Strategic Surprise and Deception."

²⁵ Michman, Dror and Yael Mizrahi-Arnaud. "The fog of uncertainty: learning from the intelligence failures of the 1973 war." Brookings. 23 October 2017.

²⁶ Michman, "The fog of uncertainty: learning from the intelligence failures of the 1973 war."

²⁷ Review of *Head of IDF Devil's Advocate Unit Tried Repeatedly in September to Warn of Possible Hamas Attack*. 2024. The Times of Israel. January 4, 2024.

²⁸ Shultz, "Strategic Surprise and Deception."

²⁹ Bergman, Ronen, and Adam Goldman. 2023. "Israel Knew Hamas's Attack Plan More than a Year Ago." *The New York Times*, December 1, 2023, sec. World.

³⁰ Bergman, "Israel Knew Hamas's Attack Plan More than a Year Ago."

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intelligence and military community, but was met with responses of it being too ambitious and not possible.³¹ The major fault in Israeli intelligence logic was the view of the enemy as inferior and incapable. One Israeli official's interview with the *New York Times* highlighted the misreading of Hamas's movements: "The audacity of the blueprint... made it easy to underestimate."³² This misapprehension proved detrimental. The Devil Advocate's alerts were dismissed prior to 7 October 2023,³³ perhaps by virtue of the position or as a common pitfall due to the habituation of proposing conflicting judgements. Nevertheless, the system put into place precisely to prevent another strategic surprise by the Israelis failed.

Failed Warning

In July 2023, Intelligence Unit 8200, a SIGNINT intelligence corp, warned of images and signals of novel military exercises. Unit 8200 noted the alignment between the exercises and the Jericho Wall document, but the "colonel in the Gaza division applauded the analysis... [saying that] the exercise was part of a "totally imaginative" scenario, not an indication of Hamas's ability to pull it off."³⁴ The Unit's warning was ultimately dismissed as provoking and unreliable.³⁵

Additional surveillance warnings were issued by a young women's combat brigade, the IDF's *tatzpitaniyot*. They reported activity along the southern border with Gaza, but their warnings were disregarded.³⁶ The women reported to *Haaretz* that their warnings were not moved up the chain of command because of inherent sexism: "chauvinism"³⁷ was potentially one of the key failures in Israel's inability to defend against Hamas's attack.

Furthermore, Egyptian and American intelligence sources provided Israeli officials with early warning, albeit ambiguously on the part of the Egyptians. An Egyptian intelligence agency informed Israel that 'something big' was going to happen soon.³⁸ This advance warning was vague, and therefore hard to act upon, but it was still not taken seriously. The CIA warned of possible violent flare-ups in Gaza twice before 7 October 2023: the first classified report was issued on September 28th, 2023 and noted potential rocket launchings by Hamas; the second one was issued just two days before the attack on October 5th, 2023.³⁹ None of these warnings were delivered to high Israeli government officials or taken at face value as imminent threats.⁴⁰ Money trails stemming from Iran directly to Hamas also could

³¹ Bergman, "Israel Knew Hamas's Attack Plan More than a Year Ago."

³² Bergman, "Israel Knew Hamas's Attack Plan More than a Year Ago."

³³ *Head of IDF Devil's Advocate Unit Tried Repeatedly in September to Warn of Possible Hamas Attack*. Times of Israel.

³⁴ Bergman, "Israel Knew Hamas's Attack Plan More than a Year Ago."

³⁵ Shultz, "Strategic Surprise and Deception."

³⁶ *Review of Surveillance Soldiers Charge Sexism a Factor in Their Oct. 7 Warnings Being Ignored*. The Times of Israel. November 19, 2023.

³⁷ Lecker, Maya. "On October 7, Sexism in Israel's Military Turned Lethal." *Haaretz*, November 20, 2023, sec. Haaretz Today.

³⁸ "Egypt Intelligence Official Says Israel Ignored Repeated Warnings of 'Something Big.'" 2023. The Times of Israel. October 9, 2023.

³⁹ Barnes, Julian E., Adam Entous, Edward Wong, and Adam Goldman. "C.I.A. Reports Contained General Warnings of Potential Gaza Flare-Up." *The New York Times*, October 13, 2023.

⁴⁰ Beaumont, Peter. "Israeli Intelligence Leak Details Extent of Warnings over Hamas Attack." *The Guardian*, November 28, 2023, sec. World news.

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have provided warning, but they too were disregarded.⁴¹

While the warnings were registered, they were not agreed upon, believed, or moved up the chain of command. The different actors involved in decision-making in Israel and the various intelligence and IDF units issuing warnings neither coordinated responses to the alerts nor acted uniformly to prepare defensively. As noted by Lani Kass and Jack London, coordination between the military and the intelligence community are essential in forming grand strategy and countering surprise, denial, and deception.⁴² Israeli forces lacked alignment except in the case that this brush aside of alarm was uniformly justified by an inaccurate belief that Hamas was inferior to Israel. Additionally, Hamas was in transition to apparent governance of the Gaza Strip, constraining its use of force to deceive Israel and confirm bias. Overall, the IDF did not trust any departmental analysis of Hamas’s capabilities to attack on such a scale: the Israeli military was incapable of imagining the unimaginable. Whether this was a failure of intelligence or a cognitive bias, analytic managers conflated assessments, building intentions solely off capabilities: this was a failure of structural policy and assessment in practice. Intelligence officials failed to implement the practices put into place after the Yom Kippur War to prevent strategic surprise and deception. The IDF had the steps in place to prevent another surprise, but a breakdown of the Devil’s Advocate

system—whether due to bias or the misinterpretation and combination of capabilities and intent—led to the IDF ostensibly dismissing the warnings.

Hamas’s ‘Transition’

While Hamas did not hide its military exercise, it did maintain a public impression of refraining from engagement with Israel. Hamas began its deception in its ‘transition’ from militancy to governance of the Gaza Strip. It campaigned for Gazans to work in Israel: by harnessing social improvement, Hamas tricked Israel into thinking its ideological violence was contained.⁴³ Furthermore, these workers were recruited by Hamas to supplement open-source intelligence to assist in mapping out kibbutzim and Israeli territory to attack on 7 October 2023.⁴⁴ Hamas also listened to Israeli political and military commentary on news outlets, and used Google and other search engines to obtain public information that would be beneficial in their attack plans. Meanwhile, the IDF believed that Hamas was complacent and therefore they refocused their resources on the West Bank.⁴⁵ Many reservists were moved from Gaza. This decrease in monitoring was one factor leading to Israel’s downfall: in addition to minimal surveillance of Gaza, the IDF ceased keeping track of handheld radios, judging the signals monitoring a “waste of effort.”⁴⁶ Instead, the IDF began to over-rely upon signals intelligence (SIGINT) and

⁴¹ Samuels, Ben. 2024. “‘Notoriously Opaque’: The Money Trails Linking Hamas, Al-Qaida, Sudan and Iran.” *Haaretz*, January 9, 2024, sec. Middle East.

⁴² Lani Kass, J. Phillip “Jack” London, *Surprise, Deception, Denial and Warning: Strategic Imperatives*, Orbis, Volume 57, Issue 1, 2013: 61.

⁴³ Nakhoul, Samia, and Jonathan Saul. “How Hamas Duped Israel as It Planned a Devastating Attack.” *Reuters*, October 9, 2023, sec. Middle East.

⁴⁴ Hubbard, “Behind Hamas’s Bloody Gambit to Create a ‘Permanent’ State of War.”

⁴⁵ Bergman, “How Years of Israeli Failures on Hamas Led to a Devastating Attack.”

⁴⁶ Rathbone, John Paul, and Neri Zilber. 2023. “How Israel’s Spymasters Misread Hamas.” *Financial Times*, November 9, 2023.

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communications intelligence (COMINT) from phones. Little did they know, Hamas explicitly told its military branch to cease communication regarding attacks on phones and to only use walkie-talkies.⁴⁷

Technology Reliance

Additionally, the IDF believed that its ubiquitous border technology and Iron Dome air defense system would deter Hamas. On October 1st, 2023, Tzachi Hanegbi, Israeli National Security Advisor, said, “Hamas is very, very restrained.”⁴⁸ Even Jake Sullivan, U.S. National Security Advisor, believed that Hamas was adamant on avoiding war, “bolster[ing]” its rule of governance over military action.⁴⁹ Israeli defense and security officials relied upon the concept of mitigation of conflict, with the mistaken belief that the Israeli border defenses “were enough to keep Hamas contained.”⁵⁰ However, the most important misjudgment of Israeli defense decision-makers was regarding Hamas’s employment of weapons and technology. Israeli leaders “failed to grasp the way Hamas would combine relatively simple tools into a sophisticated, multi-pronged attack that outmaneuvered a much larger, more powerful army.”⁵¹ This technological pomposity led to Israel’s failure to defeat otherwise ‘inferior’ technology.⁵² Hamas even engaged in operational deception during the 7 October 2023 attack when it deployed rockets, underlining the misperception

that attack was not the goal—Hamas was merely continuing the ceasefire status-quo of the occasional rocket launching. Through its deception, Hamas exposed the fragile state of Israeli defense, reliant on technology and failures in intelligence-gathering to understand the true intentions and capabilities of its adversary.

Vulnerabilities

Hamas also exploited Israeli vulnerability for its own advantage. Israeli news, social media, and commentary on political ongoing provided open-source intelligence into Israel’s fragility. Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu’s government is controversial: he has been involved in multiple corruption trials and his global approval ratings are low.⁵³ The polar divide in Israeli civilian dialogue and support prior to 7 October 2023 provided for vulnerability. Hamas was “embolden[ed]”⁵⁴ by Israel’s weakness and attacked its typically stronger counterpart, shattering Israeli morale.

Denial

Denial, a tactic to achieve deception, was twofold in relation to the events of 7 October 2023. First, Hamas denied information access and intelligence to Israel. Its ability to do so highlights its incredible counterintelligence capabilities. Second, the Israeli mentality denied the creative possibility that Hamas could indeed attack in such a manner. An Israeli hubris and superiority

⁴⁷ Shultz, “Strategic Surprise and Deception.”

⁴⁸ Robbins, James S. n.d. “Hamas Thinks They Are Winning - the American Spectator | USA News and Politics” The American Spectator | USA News and Politics. Accessed April 4, 2024.

⁴⁹ Hubbard, “Behind Hamas’s Bloody Gambit to Create a ‘Permanent’ State of War.”

⁵⁰ Hubbard, “Behind Hamas’s Bloody Gambit to Create a ‘Permanent’ State of War.”

⁵¹ Hubbard, “Behind Hamas’s Bloody Gambit to Create a ‘Permanent’ State of War.”

⁵² Rathbone, “How Israel’s Spymasters Misread Hamas.”

⁵³ Dages, Holly. 2024. “Netanyahu Might Be Losing Ground, but His Politics Still Resonate with Most Israelis.” Atlantic Council. March 6, 2024.

⁵⁴ Bergman, “How Years of Israeli Failures on Hamas Led to a Devastating Attack.”

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complex led to the denial of fact: cognitive bias proved detrimental when IDF officials received warnings and chose to believe that Hamas was incapable of grand-scale attack. 7 October 2023 proved Hamas's sophisticated capabilities, destructive intent, and the manners in which the Israeli government failed to overcome a groupthink mentality of being an impenetrable military superpower. The attack occurring despite early warning is proof of an Israeli failure of imagination.

Additional denial transpired when the political wing of Hamas was left unaware of the attack plan, and the militants involved were kept in the dark until the morning of the attack.⁵⁵ They were denied information about the attack so that they could hold reasonable guilt and not be intercepted by Israeli intelligence. Nonetheless, the militants still practiced military exercises in public, and some IDF border guards noted this with concern.⁵⁶ However, an adversary's strategic changes in deception are slow and incremental, done so in an overt manner to justify unalarming behavior.⁵⁷ Hamas practicing military exercises in public led the IDF to deem these alerts of deviation from the norm as alarmists instead of realistic.⁵⁸ Plans of attack were not discussed on mobile phones, and the handheld radios that Israeli Intelligence Combat Unit 8200 recently stopped monitoring were used instead for communication.⁵⁹ This ensured that Israeli intelligence was denied further information about the attack. These means of deception proved imperative in creating a false sense of security and

complacency within the IDF and the Israeli government.

Lessons in Intelligence Studies and Tradecraft

7 October 2023's intelligence failure underscores the critical importance of embedding devil's advocacy and continuous questioning into analytic tradecraft to mitigate systemic biases. The attack's occurrence can largely be attributed to systemic issues, the sophisticated denial and deception employed by Hamas, an overreliance on supposed technological superiority, and a dismissive attitude toward certain intelligence inputs. These factors converged, creating a blind spot that facilitated large-scale surprise.

Systemic failures in Israeli intelligence highlight how the absence of structured devil's advocacy and/or red cells may allow flawed assumptions to persist unchallenged. The breakdown of a rigorous analytic process inhibits critical examination of capabilities and intent. In the case of 7 October 2023, early warnings, including explicit intelligence from Unit 8200, reports from IDF surveillance units, and signals from American and Egyptian intelligence, were largely ignored. This was compounded by a deep-seated cognitive bias within Israeli decision-making circles that underestimated Hamas as a serious military threat. Assumptions of a Hamas shift from militancy to governance further reinforced a false sense of security.

Cognitive biases entrenched within Israeli leadership led to the dismissal of credible indicators, such as the 'Jericho Wall' plan and overt military exercises by Hamas. Without the

⁵⁵ Hubbard, "Behind Hamas's Bloody Gambit to Create a 'Permanent' State of War."

⁵⁶ Beaumont, "Israeli Intelligence Leak Details Extent of Warnings over Hamas Attack."

⁵⁷ Shultz, "Strategic Surprise and Deception."

⁵⁸ Shultz, "Strategic Surprise and Deception."

⁵⁹ Bergman, "How Years of Israeli Failures on Hamas Led to a Devastating Attack."

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deliberate incorporation of dissenting perspectives, Israeli intelligence failed to disrupt the collective overconfidence that left the nation vulnerable. Strengthening systemic practices of devil’s advocacy is essential in analytic tradecraft to ensure that all threats, regardless of initial plausibility, are evaluated rigorously.

Hamas’s use of deception demonstrates how adversaries can exploit gaps in tradecraft. Through its careful control of operational details and dissemination of intent, Hamas effectively bypassed Israeli monitoring systems. Communications were deliberately conducted over unmonitored channels, while overt political and social activities created an illusion of governance. These calculated efforts to mislead analysts capitalized on Israeli internal divisions, as well as overconfidence in the Israeli assessment of Hamas. This deception succeeded in part due to it not being countered by critical intelligence scenarios. The incorporation of devil’s advocacy is therefore imperative to countering adversarial attempts of deception.

The overreliance on technology within Israeli intelligence underscores how tradecraft can falter without a strong emphasis on analytic questioning. Israeli agencies leaned heavily on signals intelligence (SIGINT) and communications intelligence (COMINT), while overlooking other critical sources, such as human intelligence (HUMINT) and open-source intelligence (OSINT). This narrow focus failed to detect Hamas’s unconventional preparations, such as the use of Gazan workers and publicly available maps to aid their attack. The events of 7 October 2023 illustrate the essential need for

comprehensive tradecraft to counter overconfidence. Addressing these failures requires a fundamental shift in intelligence practices toward a culture of humility and rigorous self-critique. The embedding of reform into the core of analytic tradecraft may facilitate governments reducing their susceptibility to strategic surprises while strengthening their overall preparedness.

Conclusion

Israel’s false belief that Hamas was deterred led to its falling victim to Hamas’s scheme of deception. Hamas’s catastrophic success “capitaliz[ed] on hubris... and self-delusion.”⁶⁰ According to three Israeli defense officials in an interview with the *New York Times*, “nobody believed the situation was serious enough to wake up Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu.”⁶¹ They could not comprehend that Hamas had successfully attacked one of the greatest contemporary military forces, Israel, and was even able to catch it off-guard. Conclusions of the 7 October 2023 events indicate that, while strategic surprise occurred, it should not have been a tactical surprise. Israel’s intelligence failure and susceptibility to Hamas’s 7 October 2023 attack is attributed to the conflation of capabilities and intent, misapprehension of threat levels, and cognitive bias. Overall, Hamas’s success highlights the challenge of asymmetric warfare and countering ideological actors. The intelligence failure of 7 October 2023 evidences the imperative nature of remaining vigilant, utilizing all-source intelligence, and preparing robust strategic planning for all possible national security events—including the unimaginable. The events of October 7 demonstrate the dangers of cognitive

⁶⁰ Kass, *Surprise, Deception, Denial and Warning: Strategic Imperatives*: 59.

⁶¹ Bergman, “How Years of Israeli Failures on Hamas Led to a Devastating Attack.”

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bias and overconfidence in intelligence and decision-making processes. Moving forward, intelligence agencies and policymakers must adopt a posture of humility and rigorously challenge their own assumptions to avoid future strategic surprises. The use of all-source intelligence, alongside a culture of robust internal

critique, will be essential in adapting to evolving threats and safeguarding national security.

The most important takeaway from 7 October 2023 on a strategic level is that, for effective military and political planning, humility is key: hubris is disastrous.

Author Biography

Julia Shufro is a Senior Consultant in the Washington, D.C. metro area who specializes in emerging technologies, counterterrorism, and irregular warfare. Prior to her time in DC, Julia worked at the United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs (UNODA), where she was a Secretariat member of the Biological Weapons Convention (BWC) Implementation Support Unit (ISU), Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) on the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space (PAROS), and Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW). Julia received her Master of Arts in Law and Diplomacy (MALD) from The Fletcher School, with focus on international security and law. This publication was her final research submission for her graduate studies. Julia obtained her bachelor’s degree in history and French from Tufts University.

Photo by Tomer Dahari: <https://www.pexels.com/photo/soldiers-walking-on-a-brown-field-11452420/>

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